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Project Deliverable

D4.3: Integration in IC and DFW

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Document history

Version	Date	Changes	By	Reviewed
0.1	2023-21-11	First draft	Frederik Trier Møller, Caroline Eves, Thor Grønborg Junker	Frederik Trier Møller
1.0	2023-18-12	Final version	Frederik Trier Møller	Frederik Trier Møller Roxana Merino Martinez Joakim Dillner

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides documentation regarding the status of **D4.4 Integration in IC and DFW**.

In collaboration with WP6 and WP10, the goal was to develop approaches to integrate exposure to nutrients, chemicals, and additives in HEAP's Information Commons and Knowledge Network (**M42**).

Although WP4 gained access to the HEAP consortium's secure GDPR-compliant HPC resources and successfully uploaded the developed purchase data pipeline described within, the pipeline was run in Hopsworks in a manual curated session at the last BYOD data meeting. Hopsworks is working on an R Studio implementation to be run directly from Hopsworks to ensure the pipeline can run on the HEAP platform. The next step is testing the same pipeline in R Studio through Hopsworks, which will be demonstrated during the next BYOD. The pipeline is already available on GitHub and can run outside the Hopsworks environment.

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1 Introduction

Deliverable 4.3 provides documentation regarding the status of **D4.3 Integration in IC and DFW**.

In collaboration with WP6 and WP10, the goal was to develop approaches to integrate exposure to nutrients, chemicals, and additives in HEAP's Information Commons and Knowledge Network at M42.

Although WP4 has gained access to the HEAP consortium's secure GDPR-compliant HPC resources at CSC and successfully uploaded the developed purchase data pipeline described in D4.2, the pipeline was run in Hopsworks in a manually curated session at the last BYOD data meeting. Hopsworks is working on an R Studio implementation to be run directly from Hopsworks. The next step is to run the same pipeline in R Studio through Hopsworks, which will be demonstrated during the next BYOD and make the pipeline accessible to non-HEAP consortium members. The pipeline is already available on GitHub (<https://github.com/ThorJunkerSSI/ConsumerData>) and can be run outside the Hopsworks environment.

2 Work progress and unexpected risks

The first version of the purchase data enrichment pipeline was run on a manually curated session in Hopsworks at the BYOD #3 workshop in November 2022. Since then, the focus has been on improving the performance of the project's Python-centric pipelines on Hopsworks. As the activity and funding of the HEAP project has been extended into 2024, it has been agreed that the implementation of R studio in Hopsworks, enabling integration of the purchase data pipeline and simulated data in Hopsworks, will be completed at the last BYOD workshop, where the HEAP governance document will also be finalised, enabling wider sharing with the research community. Please refer to D6.3: Demonstrator of the data analysis and data sharing on HEAP for more details.

3 The consumer purchase data pipeline

The pipeline and data processing have been described in a scientific paper entitled "Assessing household lifestyle exposures from consumer purchases, The My Purchases cohort".

The paper is published as an open-access article with related GitHub documentation, code and data and can be read in its entirety here:

[Assessing household lifestyle exposures from consumer purchases, the My Purchases cohort | Scientific Reports \(nature.com\)](#)

Due to restrictions regarding the use of individual-level information about health, outcomes and trajectories from registries are not available on the HEAP IC, as register-based outcomes would require copying parts of register data to the platform. However, simulated data will be made available. It could work as a testbed of various approaches to prevention, e.g., illustrating use over time to consumers (see Figure 1) or consumer purchase data's impact on health from the individual's perspective (again using simulated outcome data).

Figure 1: Example of possible approaches to prevention using simulated consumer data.

4 Collaboration and contributions from partners

This deliverable was created with partners from WP6 and WP10

The deliverable is dependent on previous deliverables and documents. It includes:

- Heap platform governance document
- D6.3: Demonstrator of the data analysis and data sharing on HEAP
- D10.2: Report on secure data platform. Documentation of the secure data platform and its integration into HEAP.

5 Scientific reporting

This deliverable is a demonstrator, and scientific reporting is not planned, but the tools implemented are published in scientific journals and made available through Hopsworks.

6 Summary

WP4 has successfully established a near real-time pipeline that enables the identification of the products sold and the enrichment of each product to allow a broad assessment of individual exposures to nutrients, chemicals, and additives.

Although WP4 has gained access to the HEAP consortium's secure GDPR-compliant HPC resources and successfully uploaded the developed purchase data pipeline, the pipeline has only been run in Hopsworks in a manual curated session at the last BYOD data meeting.

Hopsworks is working on a R Studio implementation to be run directly from Hopsworks. The next step is testing the same pipeline in R Studio through Hopsworks, which will be demonstrated during the next BYOD. The pipeline is already available on GitHub and can run outside the Hopsworks environment.

With the pipeline and simulated data available, other researchers may build and test, e.g., novel solutions to promote health using the data available, developed algorithms and pipeline performance.